

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN ON THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL CRISIS

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Abstract. In the current global financial crisis, it can be said that the development of physical education and sports, its popularization has become an extremely urgent issue, because the implementation of the state programs "Barkamol Avlod", "Sog'lom Avlod" and special programs "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" implemented in our country. In education, we intend to educate young people who are really healthy, physically strong and intellectually profound. It is obvious that our young people, who are mature in all aspects, will be able to show themselves in a positive light and bravely overcome their difficulties even in difficult conditions such as the global financial crisis.

Keywords: sport, management, global crisis, Uzbekistan, factors, characteristics.

The transition to market relations is a way to create an improved economic mechanism that ensures the effective interaction of production and the market, the proportional enrichment of self-management of state administration and enterprises, organizations, including sports organizations.[1.56-65]. The goal of state management, including physical education and sports management, is to build a strong democratic legal state and civil society in the conditions of a stable socially oriented market economy.

The process of formation of sports management in the conditions of the market economy in Uzbekistan has its own characteristics.

- First, the process of active adaptation to the methods of physical education and sports management, formed in the period before independence, continues. [3.48-52].
- Secondly, new forms and mechanisms of physical education and sports management are being created in the conditions of modern market economy and the consequences of the global financial and economic crisis in Uzbekistan.

In recent times, it can be clearly observed that this situation is increasingly reflected in the field of professional sports. for example, the creation and

development of a fitness club and its networks in the development of entrepreneurship in team sports organizations is a proof of our opinion.

The current development of physical education and sports management in Uzbekistan depends on the following factors:

- public physical education and sports are losing their position as the primary stage of the network; [5.148-155].
- the emergence and rapid development of the fitness industry;
- the emergence of commercial sports organizations, especially in the field of providing physical education and health services to the population and in the field of "big" sports; [2.90-95].
- the emergence of categories of commercial sports organizations and the increase in their types;
- the radical increase in the importance and status of public organizations;
- the intensive development of the system of professional commercial sports and related competitions;
- the role of the state in physical education and sports management
- targeted programming at all stages of physical education and sports management development and implementation.

The skill of physical education and sports management consists in mastering all its methods, connecting them correctly to physical education and sports, and having the ability to find the most effective option of management in each specific situation.

The practical aspects of physical education and sports management are aimed at solving the following specific tasks:

- transitioning to market economy relations,
- making profits,
- increasing production efficiency,
- strengthening social protection of the population,
- developing physical education and sports in the conditions of raising the moral level of people, and directed at others.

The main task of physical education and sports management is to develop and implement the principles of purpose-oriented actions necessary for the effective management of physical education and sports, taking into account the requirements of the objective laws of the development of society and generalizing the practice of economic management.

Conclusion. Taking into account above-given data it can be concluded that the formation of sports management in Uzbekistan based on the market economy is

considered as an effective way to develop sport in the country. Therefore, the article presented some characteristics and factors to develop sports management in Uzbekistan o the conditions of global crisis.

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